

RECONSTRUCTION OF MESOSCALE TEXTILE COMPOSITES USING MICRO-CT IMAGE & COMPUTER VISION ALGORITHM

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Introduction

- The field of view is inversely proportional to the magnification.
- The field of view required to capture the geometry of mesoscale RVE limits the resolution and fibre information.
- Existing computer vision algorithm is able to classify relatively low resolution scans.

Large Field of view with low resolution

High resolution with limited field of view

Chowdhury, N. T., Tao C, G. M. Pearce, S. D. C. Walsh, S. J. Latham, J. P. Middleton, and L. Beeching. "Design of an Uncontaminated Textile Cfrp Specimen Optimised for Both Mechanical Testing and X-Ray Microtomography." *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 123 (2019/08/01/ 2019): 208-21.

CT Imaging

The specimen used in this study is braided HTS40/RTM6 with a layup of $[\pm 67.5/\pm 22.5]_s$. The textile composite specimen is 31mm x 8mm and approximately 2mm thick. The specimen is encased in resin to form an Ø8mm cylinder in order to reduce the edge hardening effect associated with CT scans.

HTS40/RTM6 specimen model (left) / photo (right)

Apparatus set up

X-ray current	220 μ A	Specimen distance	8mm
X-ray Energy	60 kV	accumulations	5
Acquisition Time	27:41:38	Number of voxels	2520*2520*2440
Sample filter	1.5mm Al	Field of view	9.18*9.18*8.89 mm
Exposure time	2.4	Voxel size	3.6438 μ m

The scan was performed at Tyree X-ray lab, UNSW, Sydney. The tomographic reconstruction was carried out in the local computer cluster using QMango software.

Image Process

Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) is a feature descriptor used for human reconnection. It computes the edge orientation within a window of specified size and provides the weighted gradient value at equally spaced angles between 0° and 180°.

The HOG Algorithm is used to compute the edge direction of the fibre and the result can be used to classify the volume into different tows.

Dalal, N. and B. Triggs. *Histograms of oriented gradients for human detection*. in 2005 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR'05). 2005.

Result

Image shows the 3d rendering of the geometry

Ongoing Work

- Modelling based on the acquired geometry
- Exploring Different image method such as neutron tomography
- Digital volume correlation based on the scan result of in-situ tensile test

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